

A New Spot Test for the Detection of Cobalt

S. B. SAXENA*, R. N. AGARWAL & A. GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, Madhav Institute of
Technology & Science, Gwalior (M.P.)

Manuscript received 6 August, 1976, accepted
10 February 1977.

THE authors earlier reported that 2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methyl-acetophenone oxime (HNMA) forms a bright-red chelate with cobalt at pH 4.5 and above¹.

The colour of the metal complex is so characteristic and sharp that it can form the basis for a reliable spot-test for the detection of cobalt.

Under the condition of the test (pH 5), Pd²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Fe³⁺ are other metals which give solid chelates of different colours. Al³⁺, Cr³⁺, Ca²⁺, Ba²⁺, Sr²⁺, Li⁺, Mg²⁺, Mn²⁺, Ce⁴⁺, Zr⁴⁺, Th⁴⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, Hg²⁺, Bi³⁺ neither give a solid complex nor appear to make any characteristic colour change to interfere with the test.

Experimental

Place a few grains (25 mgms) of crystalline sodium acetate, a drop of the solution to be tested and a drop of 1.0% ethanolic solution of the reagent on a spot plate in the order. The formation of a deep red precipitate indicates the presence of Cobalt.

Identification limit : 1 μ
Dilution limit : 1 : 50,000
1 : 25,000 (in presence of interfering ions).

As expected, copper, palladium, nickel, iron and zinc interfere with the test. Interference due to copper and palladium can be overcome by precipitating out these metals at pH 1-2 and performing the test with supernatant liquid as above. Iron (Fe³⁺) can be masked by adding a drop of 10% sodium or potassium fluoride solution before the addition of the reagent.

It is not possible to test cobalt in the presence of a large excess of zinc and nickel which give canary yellow and green precipitates respectively under test conditions. However, cobalt can be tested reliably in the presence of upto 5 fold excess of these metals. The colour of the precipitate in such cases will vary from red to brown depending upon the concentration of the interfering metals viz., nickel and zinc.

Amongst the anions NO₃⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, SO₄²⁻, ClO₄⁻ were tried and were found not to interfere with the test even when present in severalfold excess. Desai and Gandhi² used *o*-hydroxy propiophenone and butyrophenone oximes for spot test detection of Iron.

* For correspondence

References

1. R. Nath, S. C. Nautiyal, and H. Singh, *Labdev, J. Sci., Tech.* (India), 1974, 12A (2), 53-8.
2. M. N. Desai and M. H. Gandhi. *Chem., & Industry* 1968, 20, 653.

A Variable Frequency, Variable Displacement, Glass Encased Gas Recirculation Pump

JOHN CECE, KASTURI GADGIL, KRISHNA MAIR
and
RICHARD D. GONZALEZ*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rhode Island,
Kingston, Rhode Island 02881 U.S.A.

Manuscript received 3 March 1976, revised 27 January
1977, accepted 24 February 1977.

RECIRCULATION pumps, provide a more satisfactory way of studying kinetics and mechanisms of reactions taking place in static reactors as a more homogeneous gas phase is assured. In particular, for studies occurring at the surface of a solid catalyst, mass transfer effects and concentration gradients can lead to erroneous interpretation of the data. If the gas phase is continually circulated over the solid catalyst, these effects can be diminished although not entirely eliminated. In the design of a recirculation pump, it is essential that the pump surface be contamination free. Several designs have been reported in the literature¹⁻⁴ but none are entirely satisfactory. Some of these designs incorporate metal parts and lubricants exposed to the gas phase whereas others, rely on gravity for the downstroke resulting in an unequal pressure differential for the upward and downward motion of the piston. There is one design which is nearly satisfactory⁴, however the electronic design is cumbersome in that energization of the solenoids is accomplished by a microswitch which is not only expensive but needs frequent replacement.

To circumvent this problem, we have incorporated several of the better features of the pump described by Chambers et al.⁴, and redesigned the electronics in such a way that microswitches and cams are not necessary. The result is the Variable Frequency, Variable Displacement pump described in this communication. We have found this pump to be inexpensive in its construction as well as trouble-free in its operation.

*To whom queries concerning this paper should be made.